

Physiotherapy Based on a Biobehavioral Approach with or Without Orthopedic Manual Physical Therapy in the Treatment of Nonspecific Chronic Low Back Pain: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Abstract

Objective. To compare the effectiveness of a biobehavioral approach with and without orthopedic manual physical therapy on the intensity and frequency of pain in patients diagnosed with nonspecific chronic low back pain. Methods. A single-blind randomized controlled trial. Fifty patients were randomly allocated into two groups: one group received biobehavioral therapy with orthopedic manual physical therapy, and the other group received only biobehavioral therapy. Both groups completed a total of eight sessions, with a frequency of two sessions per week. The somatosensory, physical, and psychological variables were recorded at baseline and during the first and third month after initiation of treatment. Results. In both groups, the treatment was effective, presenting significant differences for all the variables in the time factor. There were no significant differences between groups in intensity or frequency of pain, with a large effect size (>0.80), but there were intragroup differences for both intervention groups at one- and three-month follow-up. There were also no significant differences between groups in the secondary variables during the same follow-up period. Conclusions. The results of this study suggest that orthopedic manual physical therapy does not increase the effects of a treatment based on biobehavioral therapy in the short or medium term, but these results should be interpreted with caution.

Key Words: Nonspecific Chronic Low Back Pain; Biobehavioral Approach; Chronic Pain; Physical Therapy; Coping Skills

Introduction

Low back pain (LBP) is the most prevalent musculoskeletal problem and the main cause of disability in society [1–3]. Current research supports that this problem carries a high incidence of chronicity, which entails a great socioeconomic cost [2]. Chronic low back pain (CLBP) that is not preceded by any pathology is referred to as nonspecific CLBP. It accounts for 90% of cases according to the World Health Organization [1]. For decades, the diagnosis of LBP has been pathoanatomical. However, several research studies have determined that imaging findings do not correlate with the patient's perceived disability and pain [2]. Patients with CLBP have been shown to present alterations in processing information through the central nervous system [4]. The influence of psychdisability factors might contribute to the development of some maladaptive neuroplastic changes at the medullary and supramedullary levels, which could be the reason for recurrence of pain [4,5]. There are many therapeutic options for the treatment of CLBP. Orthopedic manual physical therapy, therapeutic exercise, and therapeutic patient education have independently been shown to have beneficial effects in patients with CLBP, but they differ in the maintenance of mid- to long-term change. The application of orthopedic manual physical therapy in patients with CLBP has been demonstrated to be a powerful tool in the modulation of pain. However, it has been observed that the effects produced are maintained only in the short term [6–8]. On the other hand, many studies have shown that the application of therapeutic exercise in this population produces a maintenance of change for the medium term [9, 10]. Changes generated by therapeutic exercise are produced by some neuromodulatory mechanisms, such as the analgesia produced by the opioid route or the analgesia produced by releasing endogenous cannabinoids [11–15]. At the same time, therapeutic patient education is a tool that aims to change the maladaptive beliefs that may interfere with the perception of pain. It provides the

patient with coping skills and strategies [16,17]. The biobehavioral approach has been shown to be effective in several conditions of chronic musculoskeletal pain [18–22]. The objective of biobehavioral intervention is to change the pain experience, considering three response systems of emotional experiences (behavior, cognition, or physiological reactivity) [23–25]. Multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary interventions that integrate Cognitive Behavioral Therapy with other approaches may represent the future direction of the management of chronic back pain, with treatments modified for specific circumstances and stakeholders [18]. On the one hand, behavioral treatment is based on operant conditioning. It promotes, in patients with chronic pain, an increase of activity levels, caused by various types of positive reinforcement [22], and it is important also because it deals with problematic pain behaviors [21]. Operant theory hypothesizes that all behavior is sensitive to the effects of environmental responses to that behavior. Then, cognitive treatment deals with those maladaptive beliefs that produce an exacerbation and the recurrence of symptoms, and it is performed by using cognitive distraction techniques and sensory–motor restructuring in order to change the patient’s pain expectations; it is closely related to information that a patient learns during Therapeutic Patient Education [19,20]. On the other hand, physiological reactivity treatment uses progressive relaxation, decreasing arousal and sympathetic activation [21]. Frequent cooccurrence of the unconditioned stimulus of pain with innocuous stimuli (conditioned stimuli) that are present simultaneously with the painful stimulation leads to the development of pain-related responses to these formerly neutral stimuli [26]. Relaxation or similar techniques are aimed at producing classical disappearance of these relationships. Relaxation is often used in pain treatments [27]. The main objective of this research was to compare the effectiveness of a biobehavioral approach with and without orthopedic manual physical therapy on the intensity and

frequency of pain in patients diagnosed with nonspecific CLBP at three-month follow-up. The secondary objective was to evaluate the effectiveness of these interventions on somatosensory, physical, and psychological variables.

Methods

Study Design This study was a single-blind randomized controlled study. The sample was composed of patients with nonspecific CLBP. The study protocol follows the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) statement on randomized trials of nonpharmacological treatment. As recommended by the CONSORT guidelines, Figure 1 presents a flow diagram for this trial [28]. All procedures were approved by the Ethics Committee of La Paz University Hospital (PI-2567) and conform to the regulations of the Declaration of Helsinki. After receiving detailed information about the study, all participants provided written informed consent.

Recruitment of Participants A total of 50 patients with nonspecific CLBP diagnosis were randomly allocated into one of two parallel treatment groups using GraphPad software (GraphPad Software Inc, La Jolla, CA, USA). The patients were recruited from the La Salle University Centre for Advanced Studies between February 2017 and June 2018. Patients with nonspecific CLBP were selected if they met the inclusion criteria, defined by National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) in the LBP guidelines as a “tension, soreness and/or stiffness in the lower back region for which it is not possible to identify a specific cause of the pain. Several structures in the back, including the joints, discs and connective tissues, may contribute to symptoms” [29]. The inclusion criteria are as follows: a) LBP for at least the prior three months; b) LBP of nonspecific nature; c) men and women aged 18 to 65 years; d) LBP for at least 10 days per month; and e) an intensity of pain between 3 and 10 on the visual analog scale (VAS). The presence of any of the following resulted in exclusion: a) the presence

of neurological signs (such as weakness perceived in the lower limbs); b) having undergone back surgery; c) specific spinal pathology; d) a recent trauma; e) pregnant women; f) illiteracy; g) understanding or communication difficulties; and h) insufficient language comprehension to follow measurement instructions. Procedure After consenting to participate, all participants were given an initial evaluation; they received a sociodemographic questionnaire to complete on the day of measurement, including sex and education level data. Next, each participant had to complete a set of self-report measures, and finally, the patients received a manual physical examination, including an assessment of the lumbar region, an evaluation of their motor control, extensor endurance, temporal summation magnitude, and a two-point discrimination test. These self-reports and the physical testing were conducted on the day of the first measurement (pretreatment), at the end of the intervention (post-treatment), and at three-month follow-up.

Primary Outcome Measures Pain Intensity The VAS was used to measure pain intensity before and after each treatment. The VAS is a 100-mm line with two end points representing the extreme states of “no pain” and “the maximal pain imaginable.” It has been shown to have good retest reliability ($r = 0.94$, $P < 0.001$) and a minimal detectable change of 15.0 mm [30,31].

Frequency of Pain The frequency of pain was evaluated by counting the days with pain during last month.

Intake and Frequency of Medication Medication intake and frequency were evaluated by counting the days that the patient had taken medication for low back pain in the last month.

Secondary Outcome Measures Temporal Summation Magnitude In this test, Von Frey monofilaments were used. Patients were placed in a prone decubitus position on the stretcher, and measurements were taken 1 cm lateral to the spinous apophysis of L4 and in the lateral epicondyle of the nondominant forearm. Initially, a single stimulus was applied on these points, then the patient assessed the pain intensity of the stimulus using

the VAS. After that, 10 rhythmic stimuli were applied on the same point, guided by a metronome at 60 bpm [32, 33]. The temporal summation effect on pain was calculated as the difference between the mean rating of the three repetitions of one stimulus and the mean rating of the three repetitions of 10 stimuli [34].

Two-Point Discrimination Test A two-point discrimination test was performed with an esthesiometer. This test presented an intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) of 0.81. Participants were positioned comfortably in a prone decubitus position. The evaluator made a mark 1 cm lateral to the spinous apophysis of L3 on the dominant side of the patient. Testing was commenced with callipers set at 70 mm based on a protocol detailed by Nolan [35]. The distance between the points was decreased by 10 mm until the patient was able to perceive only one point instead of two. Patients were instructed to say “one” when they felt one point or “two” when they felt two points. The evaluator made three measurements and calculated the total mean [36].

Extensor Endurance Extensor endurance was evaluated with the Ito test. Patients were positioned in a prone decubitus position while holding their sternum off the floor. The evaluator placed a small pillow under the lower abdomen to decrease the lumbar lordosis [37]. The patients were instructed to maintain this position as long as possible, with a maximum of 300 seconds [37, 38]. The time (in seconds) in which participants maintained that position without claudication was registered. Patients with CLBP produced test–retest r values of 0.93 and 0.95 for men and women, respectively, and an ICC of 0.93 for both genders [37].

Motor Control The motor control of the lumbar region was evaluated with a Stabiliser Pressure Biofeedback unit (Chattanooga Group Inc., Chattanooga, TN, USA). A modification of the neutral position test, developed by Azevedo et al. in 2013, was performed based on the stabilizer instructions; the measurement was based on a protocol validated in a previous study and presented an ICC of 0.94 (95% confidence

interval $\frac{1}{4}$ 0.87–0.97) [39]. Patients were positioned in a supine decubitus position with the stabilizer in the lumbar region with an initial pressure of 40 mmHg and a knee flexion of 90. They were then instructed to perform a 90 hip and knee flexion with one limb, and then performed the same with the opposite limb. According to the stabilizer's protocol of treatment, the pressure should increase between 8 and 10 mmHg during the exercise. The evaluator made three measurements and calculated the total mean [40].

Low Back Disability Physical disability due to LBP was assessed using the Spanish version of the Roland-Morris Disability Questionnaire (RMDQ), which has been demonstrated as having acceptable psychometric properties [41]. The RMDQ is a 24-item self-administered questionnaire, and the total score ranges from 0 to 24, 24 being the score that marks the highest level of disability [41]. It has a Cronbach's alpha ranging between 0.84 and 0.93 and test-retest reliability ranging between 0.72 and 0.91. A two- to five-point change from baseline is considered clinically important [42, 43].

Pain-Related Fear of Movement Pain-related fear of movement was assessed using the 11-item Spanish version of the Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia, whose reliability and validity have been demonstrated (internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha = 0.78) [44]. The Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia consists of two subscales, one related to Fear of Activity and the other related to Fear of Harm. The final score can range between 11 and 44 points, with higher scores indicating greater perceived kinesiophobia [44]. The minimal detectable change score was 5.6 (45).

Pain Catastrophizing The Spanish version of the Pain Catastrophizing Scale assesses the degree of pain catastrophizing; it is a reliable and valid form of measurement. It is composed of 13 items, with a three-factor structure of Rumination, Magnification, and Helplessness that must be answered by a numeric value between 0 (not at all) and 4 (all the time), with a maximum score of 52 points; higher scores indicate greater pain catastrophizing [45]. The minimal

detectable change was identified as 9.1 points [46]. Self-Efficacy Self-efficacy was assessed through the Spanish version of the Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale (CPSS), which has been demonstrated to have acceptable psychometric properties [47]. The scale was developed to measure perceived self-efficacy and ability to cope with the consequences of pain in chronic pain patients. This scale is a 19-item self-administered instrument with three domains that assess Self-Efficacy for Pain Management, Physical Functioning, and Coping with Symptoms, with higher scores indicating greater self-efficacy for managing pain [47]. The CPSS presented a reliability of 0.88, 0.87, and 0.90 for the Pain Management subscale, Physical Functioning subscale, and Coping with Symptoms subscale, respectively [48]. Global Perception of Change Global perception of change was assessed using the Global Rating of Change scale, in which the patient is asked to quantitatively assess the improvement experienced since the treatment began. The score fluctuates between -5 and +5, with -5 being "I have worsened dramatically," 0 being "I have not improved at all," and +5 being "I am completely recovered" [49]. Intervention All the patients received eight treatment sessions for one month (twice per week). Each session was one-on-one, and there was a rest period of 48 to 72 hours between sessions. To be included in the analysis, each patient had to participate in at least seven sessions. The control group (G0) received a physiotherapy approach based on a biobehavioral paradigm. This approach consisted of therapeutic patient education for 20– 25 minutes in sessions 1, 3, 5, 7, and 8, with the support of a PowerPoint presentation using diagrams, images, and text. The objectives of therapeutic patient education were to act on the patient's maladaptive coping beliefs, to promote active strategies, and to increase patient self-efficacy (Supplementary appendix 1). During sessions 2, 4, and 6, the therapist performed a review of the concepts acquired in the previous session. Biobehavioral strategies were

implemented within therapeutic patient education: experiential motor restructuring (it is called experiential because it is used to check the patient's pain perceptions in order to disconfirm his/her pain expectations by using a distraction task while the patient performs a potentially painful movement), sensorial reinterpretation (this is a cognitive technique, in which the patient is forced to repeatedly to assess his/her pain in order to eliminate magnification biases), progressive Jacobson relaxation, and a program of observed action and motor imagery (Supplementary appendix 2). G0 received a therapeutic exercise program, which was based on stabilization exercises of the lumbar region (synergy of the transverse muscle, multifidus, and pelvic floor muscles). Exercise sessions were individualized and supervised by the therapist. The therapeutic exercise program increased in difficulty and intensity in each session. All the patients were instructed to stop exercise when they experienced pain. The duration of the therapeutic exercise program was 20–25 minutes per session, and all patients were instructed to perform the therapeutic exercise program at home at least twice a week during treatment (Supplementary appendix 3). The experimental group (G1) received the same treatment as G0, in addition to an orthopedic manual physical therapy protocol (Supplementary appendix 4). The protocol consisted of accessory mobilizations (posteroanterior), traction of the lumbar region, mobilization with movement in the coxofemoral joint, and global techniques of neural mobilization of the lumbar spine. The duration of the orthopedic manual physical therapy was 20–25 minutes per session. The therapist always performed the orthopedic manual physical therapy after the biobehavioral treatment.

Sample Size The sample size and power calculations were performed using software from the Massachusetts General Hospital's (MGH's) Biostatistics Center (Boston, MA, USA). Pain intensity, measured with the VAS, was chosen as the primary outcome measure in this study. Calculations were based on a

minimal detectable change of 15 mm in patients with low back pain [31], based on data obtained from the difference in means between pre and postintervention and between both groups of a pilot study conducted in 15 patients with nonspecific CLBP. The experimental group received treatment based on therapeutic patient education, therapeutic exercise using a biobehavioral approach, and orthopedic manual physical therapy, while the control group received the same intervention without orthopedic physical manual therapy. Both groups received a total of eight sessions, with a frequency of two sessions per week. Assuming a standard deviation of 16.18 mm, two-tailed tests, and an alpha level of 0.5, a sample size of 42 participants was generated for the study in order to have 90% power to identify an effect. Allowing for a dropout rate of 20%, we planned to recruit at least 49 patients.

Data Analysis The participants' sociodemographic and clinical variables were analyzed. The data were summarized using frequency counts, descriptive statistics, summary tables, and figures. The data analysis was performed using the Statistics Package for Social Science (SPSS 20.00, IBM Inc., Armonk, NY, USA). The Shapiro-Wilk test was used for the normality tests. The chi-square test was used for the categorical variables, which are presented as frequency and percentage. The quantitative results of the study are represented by descriptive statistics (confidence interval, mean, and standard deviation). The analysis of variance (ANOVA) test for repeated measures was used to compare numerical variables. The factors analyzed were group and time (pre- and postintervention). Partial eta-squared (η^2) was calculated as a measure of effect size (strength of association) for each main effect and interaction in the ANOVAs, with 0.01–0.059 representing a small effect, 0.06–0.139 a medium effect, and >0.14 a large effect [50]. Tests of within-patient post hoc simple effects (i.e., changes in time for all variables for each group separately) were performed by post hoc

Bonferroni corrections. The effect size (Cohen's d) was calculated for the main variables studied for multiple comparisons. According to the Cohen method, the magnitude of the effect could be considered small (0.20–0.49), medium (0.50–0.79), or large (>0.8). The significance level was set at 0.05 for all tests [50].

Results

A total of 56 patients with nonspecific CLBP were screened, 52 of whom met inclusion criteria. During the intervention, two patients from the experimental group had to leave the study for work reasons. A total of 50 patients agreed to participate in the study. Two dropouts were reported during the three months of follow-up, both from the control group. A flow chart representing the reasons why patients were lost during the three months of follow-up is presented in Figure 1. An intention-to-treat analysis was carried out, maintaining the random distribution and using the result obtained from the last measurement made before the abandonment of the study. All the patients were randomized and assigned into one of two groups: G0 ($N = 25$) or G1 ($N=25$). All the variables presented a normal distribution. No statistically significant differences were found in sociodemographic data between groups (Table 1). No statistically significant differences were found between groups for any of the variables (Table 2).

Primary outcome measures

Intensity and frequency of pain

The ANOVA test showed statistically significant differences in pain intensity for time ($F=99.20$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.683$), but no time-by-group interaction was found ($F = 0.488$, $P = 0.581$, $\eta^2 = 0.011$). A post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in both groups at post-treatment and at three-month follow-up, with a large effect size for G1 ($P < 0.001$, $d = 2.78$, and $d = 1.85$, respectively) and for G0 ($P < 0.001$, $d = 2.41$, and $d = 1.82$, respectively). Regarding pain frequency, statistically significant

differences were obtained for time ($F = 129.22$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.737$), but no time-by-group interaction was found ($F = 2.006$, $P = 0.14$, $\eta^2 = 0.042$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in both groups, with a large effect size for G1 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.17$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.63$) and for G0 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = 2.32$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001$, $d = 2.96$). In addition, only in the G0 were significant differences found between post-treatment and three-month follow-up, with a moderate effect size ($P < 0.05$, $d = 0.71$) (Table 3).

Intake and Frequency of Medication

Regarding the intake of medication, both groups showed a reduction in the intake of medication at three months of follow-up without presenting statistically significant differences between them ($P > 0.05$). The control group reduced their intake of medication by 18.2%, and the experimental group by 23.1% (Figure 2). Regarding the frequency of medication, by ANOVA there was a statistically significant difference for time ($F = 9.15$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.166$), but no time-by-group interaction was found ($F = 0.282$, $P = 0.755$, $\eta^2 = 0.006$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences only in G0 at post-treatment, with a large effect size ($P < 0.01$, $d = 0.93$) (Table 3).

Secondary outcome measures

Somatosensory variables: two-point discrimination and temporal summation

By ANOVA, there was a significant main effect of time ($F = 75.76$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.622$) but not of time-by group interaction ($F = 2.311$, $P = 0.105$, $\eta^2 = 0.048$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in both groups, with a large effect size for G1 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.22$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.93$) and for G0 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = 0.82$) and at three-

month follow-up ($P < 0.001$, $d = 0.90$). Regarding temporal summation, both in the lumbar region and in the forearm, ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference of time ($F = 21.39$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.317$; and $G0$: $F = 12.35$, $P < 0.05$, $\eta^2 = 0.212$, respectively). The post hoc analysis of the lumbar region revealed significant intragroup differences in both groups at post-treatment and at three-month follow-up, with a large effect size for $G1$ ($P < 0.01$, $d = 0.85$, and $d = 1.09$, respectively) and for $G0$ ($P < 0.001$, $d = 0.86$, and $d = 0.92$, respectively). Regarding forearm temporal summation, significant intragroup differences were found at post-treatment and at the three-month follow-up for the $G1$, with a moderate effect size ($P < 0.05$, $d = 0.66$, and $d = 0.78$, respectively), and only at post-treatment for the $G0$, with a moderate effect size ($P < 0.05$, $d = 0.75$) (Table 4)

Physical Variables: Extensor endurance and motor control

The ANOVA test showed a significant main effect of time in extensor endurance ($F = 33.51$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.422$), but no significant differences were found for time-by-group interaction ($F = 0.10$, $P = 0.905$, $\eta^2 = 0.002$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in $G1$, with a large effect size at posttreatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = -0.98$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001$, $d = -1.31$). $G0$ showed significant differences at post-treatment, with a moderate effect size ($P < 0.001$, $d = -0.73$), and also at three-month follow up, with a large effect size ($P < 0.001$, $d = -0.84$). Regarding motor control, statistically significant differences were found for time ($F = 27.39$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.373$) but not for time-by-group interaction ($F = 1.81$, $P = 0.169$, $\eta^2 = 0.038$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in $G1$, with a small effect size at post-treatment ($P < 0.01$, $d = 0.46$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.05$, $d = 0.41$), and also for $G0$ at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.04$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.01$, $d = 0.90$), with a large effect size (Table 5).

Psychological Variables and Disability: Pain Catastrophizing, Pain-Related Fear, Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy, and Disability

Regarding pain catastrophizing, the ANOVA test showed a significant main effect of time ($F= 43.96, P < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.489$) but no time-by-group interaction ($F= 0.32, P= 0.726, \eta^2 = 0.07$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in both groups, with a large effect size for G1 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001, d= 1.04$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001, d= 1.28$) and for G0 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001, d= 1.07$) and at three month follow-up ($P < 0.001, d= 1.45$). In relation to the PCS subscales, for the Magnification subscale, the ANOVA test revealed statistically significant differences of time ($F= 32.108, P < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.411$); however, no time-by-group differences were found. Similar results were found for the Rumination ($F= 34.012, P < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.425$) and Helplessness subscales ($F= 32.464, P < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.414$) (Figure 3). For pain-related fear, statistically significant differences were found for time ($F = 115.25, P < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.715$) but not for time-by-group interaction ($F = 1.16, P = 0.318, \eta^2 = 0.025$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in both groups, with a large effect size for G1 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001, d = 1.58$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001, d = 1.42$) and for G0 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001, d = 1.54$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001, d = 1.57$). In relation to the TSK-11 subscales, for the Fear of Activity subscale, the ANOVA test revealed a significant main effect of time ($F = 24.448, P < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.527$) but no time-by-group interaction. Similar results were found for the Fear of Harm subscale ($F = 34.669, P < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.612$) (Figure 4). Regarding the CPSS, the ANOVA test showed statistically significant differences for time ($F = 40.28, P < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.484$) but no time-by-group interaction ($F = 1.306, P = 0.276, \eta^2 = 0.029$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in both groups, with a moderate

effect size for G1 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = -0.72$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.01$, $d = -0.70$) and for G0 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = -0.77$) and at three-month follow-up, with a large effect size ($P < 0.001$, $d = -0.83$) (Table 6). In relation to the CPSS subscales, regarding the Coping with Symptoms subscale, the ANOVA test revealed a statistically significant main effect of time ($F = 23.159$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.350$); however, no time-by-group interaction was found. Similar results were found for the Physical Functioning ($F = 13.521$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.239$) and Pain Management subscales ($F = 27.183$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.387$) (Figure 5). Regarding disability, a statistically significant difference of time was found ($F = 73.89$, $P < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.606$), but no time-by-group interaction was found ($F = 0.578$, $P = 0.563$, $\eta^2 = 0.012$). The post hoc analysis revealed significant intragroup differences in both groups, with a large effect size for G1 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.26$) and also at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.11$) and for G0 at post-treatment ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.60$) and at three-month follow-up ($P < 0.001$, $d = 1.76$) (Table 6).

Global Perception of Change

Regarding the Global Rating of Change scale, statistically significant differences were obtained between groups at post-treatment ($P = 0.03$) in favor of the experimental group. Eight patients showed an improvement, with a score between 4 and 5 points on the Global Rating of Change scale, whereas in the control group, five patients had a score between 4 and 5 points on the scale. On the other hand, after three months of followup, there were no significant differences between groups ($P = 0.41$). At three months of follow-up in the experimental group, 13 patients had a score between 4 and 5 points on the scale, and in the control group, 11 patients showed an improvement, with a score between 4 and 5 points (Figure 6).

Discussion

The main objective of this study was to compare the effectiveness of physiotherapy based on a biobehavioral approach with or without orthopedic manual physical therapy at three-month follow-up. The data obtained in the present investigation showed that both interventions caused a statistically significant decrease in all variables, although no significant differences were found between the groups at pretreatment and at three-month follow-up. The effect sizes were large for all outcomes at three-month follow-up, except in the temporal summation of the forearm, in which both groups presented a moderate effect size. On the other hand, the experimental group presented a small effect size in the motor control variable and a moderate effect size in the self-efficacy variable, compared with the control group, which had a large effect size in those measures. Numerous studies have demonstrated significant differences in favor of combining techniques in comparison with performing them independently or with respect to medical interventions based on pharmacology [51–58]. In addition, strong scientific evidence shows that the biobehavioral approach is effective in patients with CLBP [59]; also, research studies in other chronic pain conditions have demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach in combination with the therapeutic exercise in terms of physical and psychological variables [22,57, 60,61]. Even so, we know that there is a lack of evidence on the effect of manual therapy within this multimodal approach in patients with nonspecific CLBP. Based on this, it is important to take into account that experts in chronic pain suggest that the most appropriate treatment in patients with central sensitization is the combination of therapeutic patient education and therapeutic exercise [62, 63], as theoretically in subjects with acute pain, manual therapy provides analgesic effects locally and distally, but this does not occur in subjects with subacute or chronic pain [64–66]. Our study shows that both groups obtained an improvement

superior to the minimal important change in pain intensity; a reduction of more than 15.0 mm on the VAS was demonstrated [31]. According to the results obtained in this research, a research study conducted in patients with chronic neck pain has demonstrated that there are no differences in disability and intensity of pain between the application of manual therapy and the application of therapeutic exercise [67]. Another clinical trial conducted in 2013 in patients diagnosed with nonspecific CLBP concluded that biobehavioral therapy obtained better results than manual therapy and therapeutic exercise, which were maintained at 12-month follow-up [68]. These results could be due to the importance of including active coping strategies within a biobehavioral therapy framework, which could influence cognitive and emotional factors, thus indirectly improving variables such as pain intensity. In relation to the psychosocial variables, in 2009, Meyer et al. showed that lower scores regarding fear of movement and pain catastrophizing were correlated with a lower perception of pain, these variables being, in addition, predictors of recurrence of pain episodes [69]. Our study showed that statistically significant differences with large effect sizes were obtained post-treatment and at three-month follow-up. Both groups exceeded the minimal detectable change for fear of movement and pain catastrophizing [46, 70]. In addition, the influence of negative cognitive factors such as hypervigilance and rumination has been associated with a lack of self-efficacy in this type of population [71, 72], as level of self-efficacy is a predictive variable in the recovery in patients with LBP [73]. Research studies have shown that it is important to perform an assessment of self-efficacy beliefs, as it has been observed that they are correlated with the intensity of pain and disability in turn; the presentation of passive coping strategies denotes a lack of self-efficacy in this population, potentiating nonverbal behaviors of pain such as medication intake [74–81]. Our study shows that both groups obtained an

improvement superior to the minimal important change in disability; a reduction between 2 and 5 points on the Roland-Morris Disability Questionnaire was demonstrated [42, 43]. We believe that the results of this study are due to both groups receiving the same intervention based on therapeutic exercise and therapeutic patient education, which would enhance an increase in self-efficacy and active coping strategies for both groups. According to our results, a meta-analysis carried out in 2015 on the effectiveness of different interventions in nonspecific chronic spinal pain shows that there are no significant differences between physical approaches and behavioral/psychological approaches for this pathology, concluding that more research studies should be carried out and adapted to the rehabilitation needs of each patient [60]. On the other hand, previous literature has shown that therapeutic exercise is a fundamental cause of significant improvements on functional, physical, and somatosensory variables. Regarding the discrimination of two points, it is important to note that research studies show that this alteration may be due to a distortion of the corporal representation at the level of the cortex influenced by the intensity of pain, which is related to a phenomenon of convergence between the motor, and somatosensory cortex [82–87]. At the same time, several research studies have shown that the training of tactile sensitivity in patients with nonspecific CLBP causes a significant improvement in two-point discrimination ability, in addition to a decrease in pain intensity [88,89]. Our study obtained significant improvements in both groups, but it could not be assured that this improvement was due to a sensory training as no such training was conducted in this study. It is possible that the existing relationship between the distortion of the body schema and pain intensity may have been influenced by the reduction of the last variable. Another problem that can occur in patients with chronic pain is alteration in the temporal summation of stimuli. According

to the available evidence, the improvement in this variable could be due to therapeutic exercise. Research studies performed in asymptomatic participants and patients with various conditions of chronic pain have obtained significant differences in temporal summation through the use of therapeutic exercise programs due to the hypoalgesic effects generated and improvement of the psychological factors that influence the pain experience [90–92]. Similarly, it has been observed that both muscle endurance and motor control can be altered in this population, although it is not clear whether this alteration is due to the presence of pain or a deconditioning of the musculature. A recently published systematic review showed that motor control exercises do not present significant differences with respect to other exercise modalities, according to pain intensity and disability in patients with nonspecific CLBP [93]. The results of this study do not allow us to determine what percentage of the success of treatment is due to these exercises; we cannot determine the possible results obtained using another model of therapeutic exercise either. However, we believe that the learning component and cognitive distraction presented by motor control exercises could justify their inclusion in biobehavioral therapy. It is important to emphasize that other research studies point to a possible relationship between psychological variables and alteration in endurance, demonstrating that patients with CLBP who present high levels of catastrophism also present lower endurance in the lumbar region, suggesting that improvement over psychological variables such as the effects of a biobehavioral approach could be one of the reasons for the increase in extensor endurance [94]. In relation to our results, we suspect that extensor endurance can be affected by the patient's chronicity and symptomatology because, in many cases, patients stopped the test due to the onset of pain, not due to fatigue. This explanation is possibly due to the treatment performed, given that the therapeutic exercise protocol was based on a motor

control program and did not include specific extensor endurance training. Finally, considering that the experience of pain is multifactorial, the results obtained in our research could be due to the paradigm shift produced in the patients. Louw et al., in 2017, suggested the combination of orthopedic manual physical therapy and therapeutic patient education when presented within a biomechanical model. This combination might be contradictory for patients because the therapeutic patient education models recommend active participation, improving important aspects in chronic pain such as self-efficacy, and taking into account that the application of orthopedic manual physical therapy could serve as the beginning of treatment to generate endogenous analgesia [95]. In addition, we must consider the importance of the application of manual therapy in patients with chronic pain in terms of variables such as the global perception of the change of the patient, as we observed statistically significant differences in favor of the group that received manual therapy, as well as the influence that this type of technique has on patient satisfaction or possible adherence to treatment.

Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations to consider. First, it would also have been interesting to include a more accurate control group; we could have used a group on the waiting list or a usual care group. On the other hand, there is a recall bias when it comes to the variable of medication frequency and days of pain per month. Our research only establishes results post-treatment through three months of follow-up. It will be necessary to obtain long-term results in this type of population regarding the treatments performed. Another limitation of the study to be considered is that the calculation of the sample size was made based on a pilot study, taking into account only the main variable. This could have influenced the statistical power of the estimation based on the rest of the study variables. Even so, it is important to note that the rest of the study variables behaved in the same way as the main variable. Finally, it is important to

include as a limitation that the groups presented differences in pretreatment with regards to the kinesiophobia variable and that the corresponding control variable was not included in relation to the level of physical activity. Conclusions The findings of this study show that there are no statistically significant differences in the comparison of the two treatments applied in patients with nonspecific CLBP. In the individual analysis of each intervention, the results show that in the short term and medium term, there was a decrease in the intensity and frequency of pain and an improvement in physical, somatosensory, and psychological variables. According to our results, we can conclude that orthopedic manual physical therapy does not increase the effects of physiotherapy treatment based on biobehavioral therapy; however, these results should be interpreted with caution because they have not been evaluated in the long term.

Acknowledgments The authors thank the Miraflores Health Center (Alcobendas, Madrid, Spain) for their contribution in the collection of patients for the study.

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TABLES

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for demographic outcomes (N = 50)

Measures	G ₁ (N = 25)	G ₀ (N = 25)	P Value, Independent-Samples Student <i>t</i> test or χ^2 Test
Age, y	39.88 ± 13.20	38.29 ± 13.10	0.671
BMI, kg/m ²	24.33 ± 3.29	27.17 ± 9.03	0.140
Gender			0.963
Male	11 (44)	11 (44)	
Female	14 (56)	14 (56)	
Educational level			0.589
Primary education	5 (20)	5 (20)	
Secondary education	2 (8)	4 (16)	
College education	18 (72)	16 (64)	
Marital status			0.349
Single	8 (32)	11 (44)	
Married	14 (56)	10 (40)	
Divorced	2 (8)	4 (16)	
Widow	1 (4)	0 (0.0)	
Low back pain duration, mo	71.46 ± 95.45	82.75 ± 102.51	0.689

Values are presented as mean ± SD or number (%).

BMI = body mass index; G₀ = control group; G₁ = experimental group.

*Independent-samples Student *t* test.

† χ^2 test.

Table 2. Baseline of descriptive statistics for primary and secondary outcomes

Measures	G ₁ (N = 25)	G ₀ (N = 25)	P Value
VAS	45.4 ± 10.8	50.0 ± 13.9	0.220
RMDQ	6.35 ± 4.75	5.25 ± 3.12	0.345
PF	21.88 ± 8.01	23.32 ± 5.98	0.579
L-TS	1.06 ± 0.96	1.22 ± 1.38	0.572
F-TS	0.52 ± 0.70	0.51 ± 0.89	0.979
SE	42.62 ± 26.78	41.89 ± 31.83	0.827
2-PD	5.88 ± 0.88	5.89 ± 1.34	0.927
MC	56.78 ± 9.02	58.13 ± 6.04	0.541
TSK-11			0.437
TSK-T	25.88 ± 5.96	27.55 ± 6.57	
TSK-FA	16.81 ± 3.62	17.46 ± 4.37	.
TSK-FH	9.08 ± 3.23	9.79 ± 2.45	
PCS			0.611
PCS-T	15.46 ± 11.80	13.73 ± 8.85	
PCS-R	5.77 ± 4.40	5.29 ± 3.63	.
PCS-M	3.42 ± 2.87	3.38 ± 2.31	
PCS-H	6.27 ± 5.93	5.29 ± 3.63	.
CPSS			0.698
CPSS-T	145.54 ± 29.95	137.28 ± 35.35	
CPSS-CS	36.45 ± 10.11	32.81 ± 10.78	
CPSS-PF	52.16 ± 7.95	50.61 ± 12.42	
CPSS-PM	56.91 ± 15.93	53.85 ± 18.35	
Medication F	4.12 ± 8.25	5.91 ± 8.11	0.454

Values are presented as mean ± SD.

*P < 0.05.

2-PD = 2-point discrimination; CPSS-CS = Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale Coping with Symptoms subscale; CPSS-PF = Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale Physical Functioning subscale; CPSS-PM = Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale Pain Management subscale; CPSS-T = Total Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; F-TS = left forearm temporal summation; G₀ = control group; G₁ = experimental group; L-TS = lumbar temporal summation; MC = motor control; Medication F = medication frequency; PCS-H = Pain Catastrophizing Scale Helplessness subscale; PCS-M = Pain Catastrophizing Scale Magnification subscale; PCS-R = Pain Catastrophizing Scale Rumination subscale; PCS-T = Total Pain Catastrophizing Scale; PF = pain frequency; RMDQ = Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire; SE = strength-endurance; TSK-FA = Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia Fear of Activity subscale; TSK-FH = Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia Fear of Harm subscale; TSK-T = Total Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia; VAS = visual analog scale.

Table 3. Within- and between-group results of the primary variables of pain intensity, pain frequency, and medication frequency

		Mean \pm SD			Mean Difference (95% CI); Effect Size
		Pre	Post	3 m	
VAS	G ₁	45.4 \pm 10.8	13.5 \pm 12.1	18.8 \pm 17.2	Pre-post: 31.8** (24.6 to 39.1); <i>d</i> = 2.78 Pre-3m: 26.6** (16.5 to 36.7); <i>d</i> = 1.85 Post-3m: -5.2 (-12.7 to 2.2); <i>d</i> = -0.35 Pre-post: 31.7** (23.8 to 39.6); <i>d</i> = 2.41 Pre-3m: 30.8** (19.8 to 41.8); <i>d</i> = 1.82 Post-3m: -0.9 (-9.0 to 7.2); <i>d</i> = -0.05
	G ₀	50.0 \pm 13.9	18.3 \pm 12.3	19.2 \pm 19.4	
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	-4.6 (-11.8 to 2.6); <i>d</i> = -0.37	-4.7 (-11.9 to 2.4); <i>d</i> = -0.39	-0.42 (-11.0 to 10.2); <i>d</i> = -0.02	
PF	G ₁	21.88 \pm 8.01	10.67 \pm 10.9	7.72 \pm 9.25	Pre-post: 11.34** (7.62 to 15.07); <i>d</i> = 1.17 Pre-3m: 14.16** (10.27 to 18.05); <i>d</i> = 1.63 Post-3m: 2.82 (-0.24 to 5.88); <i>d</i> = 0.29 Pre-post: 14.00** (9.95 to 18.04); <i>d</i> = 2.32 Pre-3m: 18.37** (14.14 to 22.60); <i>d</i> = 2.96 Post-3m: 4.37* (-15.23 to -7.83); <i>d</i> = 0.71
	G ₀	23.32 \pm 5.98	9.32 \pm 6.04	4.94 \pm 6.46	
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	-1.43 (-5.60 to 2.73); <i>d</i> = -0.20	1.22 (-4.40 to 6.48); <i>d</i> = 0.15	2.78 (-1.90 to 7.50); <i>d</i> = 0.34	
Med F	G ₁	4.12 \pm 8.25	0.27 \pm 0.82	1.00 \pm 3.94	Pre-post: 3.84 (-0.03 to 7.73); <i>d</i> = 0.65 Pre-3m: 3.11 (-1.47 to 7.70); <i>d</i> = 0.48 Post-3m: -0.73 (-3.25 to 1.79); <i>d</i> = -0.25 Pre-post: 5.45* (1.23 to 9.67); <i>d</i> = 0.93 Pre-3m: 3.50 (-1.48 to 8.48); <i>d</i> = 0.47 Post-3m: -1.95 (-4.71 to 0.79); <i>d</i> = -0.41
	G ₀	5.91 \pm 8.11	0.45 \pm 1.53	2.41 \pm 6.53	
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	-1.79 (-6.57 to 2.98); <i>d</i> = -0.21	-0.18 (-0.88 to 0.51); <i>d</i> = -0.14	-1.41 (-4.49 to 1.67); <i>d</i> = -0.26	

3m = three months postintervention; CI = confidence interval; G₀ = control group; G₁ = experimental group; Med F = medication frequency; PF = pain frequency; Pre = pre-intervention; Post = postintervention; VAS = visual analog scale.

P* < 0.01; *P* < 0.001.

Table 4. Within- and between-group comparison of groups of somato-sensory variables

		Mean \pm SD			Mean Difference (95% CI); Effect Size
		Pre	Post	3 m	
2-PD	G ₁	5.88 \pm 0.88	4.72 \pm 1.01	4.26 \pm 0.79	Pre-post: 1.16** (0.72 to 1.60); <i>d</i> = 1.22 Pre-3m: 1.62** (1.17 to 2.08); <i>d</i> = 1.93 Post-3m: -0.46** (0.19 to 0.74); <i>d</i> = 0.50 Pre-post: 1.02** (0.54 to 1.49); <i>d</i> = 0.82 Pre-3m: 1.13** (0.64 to 1.62); <i>d</i> = 0.90 Post-3m: 0.11 (-0.18 to 0.41); <i>d</i> = 0.10
	G ₀	5.89 \pm 1.34	4.87 \pm 1.13	4.76 \pm 1.16	
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	-0.01 (-0.65 to 0.64); <i>d</i> = -0.01	-0.14 (-0.76 to 0.47); <i>d</i> = -0.14	-0.49 (-1.07 to 0.07); <i>d</i> = -0.51	
L-TS	G ₁	1.06 \pm 0.96	0.35 \pm 0.67	0.22 \pm 0.51	Pre-post: 0.71* (0.19 to 1.22); <i>d</i> = 0.85 Pre-3m: 0.84* (0.23 to 1.44); <i>d</i> = 1.09 Post-3m: 0.12 (-0.27 to 0.52); <i>d</i> = 0.21 Pre-post: 0.93** (0.38 to 1.49); <i>d</i> = 0.86 Pre-3m: 0.94** (0.29 to 1.61); <i>d</i> = 0.92 Post-3m: 0.01 (-0.42 to 0.44); <i>d</i> = 0.01
	G ₀	1.22 \pm 1.38	0.28 \pm 0.70	0.27 \pm 0.47	
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	-0.16 (-0.84 to 0.52); <i>d</i> = -0.13	0.06 (-0.33 to 0.46); <i>d</i> = 0.1	-0.05 (-0.34 to 0.23); <i>d</i> = -0.1	
F-TS	G ₁	0.52 \pm 0.70	0.14 \pm 0.40	0.09 \pm 0.34	Pre-post: 0.38* (0.02 to 0.74); <i>d</i> = 0.66 Pre-3m: 0.43* (0.01 to 0.85); <i>d</i> = 0.78 Post-3m: 0.04 (-0.14 to 0.23); <i>d</i> = 0.13 Pre-post: 0.48* (0.09 to 0.87); <i>d</i> = 0.75 Pre-3m: 0.41 (-0.03 to 0.87); <i>d</i> = 0.63 Post-3m: -0.06 (-0.27 to 0.14); <i>d</i> = -0.27
	G ₀	0.51 \pm 0.89	0.03 \pm 0.12	0.09 \pm 0.28	
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	0.01 (-0.45 to 0.48); <i>d</i> = 0.01	0.10 (-0.07 to 0.29); <i>d</i> = 0.37	0.0 (-0.18 to 0.18); <i>d</i> = 0.0	

2-PD = 2-point discrimination; 3m = three months postintervention; CI = confidence interval; G₀ = control group; G₁ = experimental group; F-TS = left forearm temporal summation; L-TS = lumbar temporal summation; Post = postintervention; Pre = pre-intervention.

P* < 0.01; *P* < 0.001.

Table 5. Within- and between-group comparison of physical strength–endurance and motor control variables

		Mean ± SD			Mean Difference (95% CI); Effect Size
		Pre	Post	3 m	
SE	G ₁	42.62 ± 26.78	72.71 ± 34.08	87.40 ± 40.01	Pre–post: –30.09** (–42.02 to –18.16); <i>d</i> = –0.98 Pre–3m: –44.78** (–67.16 to –22.39); <i>d</i> = –1.31 Post–3m: –14.69 (–32.67 to 3.29); <i>d</i> = –0.39
	G ₀	41.89 ± 31.83	67.36 ± 37.41	83.30 ± 61.99	Pre–post: –25.47** (–38.43 to –12.50); <i>d</i> = –0.73 Pre–3m: –41.41** (–65.74 to –17.07); <i>d</i> = –0.84 Post–3m: –15.93 (–35.49 to 3.61); <i>d</i> = –0.31
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	0.73 (–16.29 to 17.75); <i>d</i> = –0.37	5.35 (–15.43 to 26.13); <i>d</i> = –0.39	4.10 (–25.77 to 33.97); <i>d</i> = –0.02	
MC	G ₁	56.78 ± 9.02	53.10 ± 6.70	53.42 ± 7.01	Pre–post: 3.68* (1.30 to 6.06); <i>d</i> = 0.46 Pre–3m: 3.36* (0.32 to 6.41); <i>d</i> = 0.41 Post–3m: –0.31 (–2.23 to 1.60); <i>d</i> = –0.04
	G ₀	58.17 ± 6.14	51.81 ± 6.04	52.71 ± 5.99	Pre–post: 6.36** (3.77 to 8.94); <i>d</i> = 1.04 Pre–3m: 5.46* (2.15 to 8.78); <i>d</i> = 0.90 Post–3m: –0.89 (–2.98 to 1.19); <i>d</i> = –0.15
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	–1.39 (–5.96 to 3.18); <i>d</i> = –0.18	1.28 (–2.34 to 4.92); <i>d</i> = 0.20	0.71 (–1.90 to 7.50); <i>d</i> = 0.11	

3m = three months postintervention; CI = confidence interval; G₀ = control group; G₁ = experimental group; MC = motor control; Post = postintervention; Pre = pre-intervention; SE = strength–endurance.

p* < 0.01; *p* < 0.001.

Table 6. Within- and between-group comparison of psychosocial variables and disability

		Mean ± SD			Mean Difference (95% CI); Effect Size
		Pre	Post	3 m	
PCS	G ₁	15.46 ± 11.8	5.58 ± 6.40	4.00 ± 4.51	Pre–post: 9.88** (5.13 to 14.63); <i>d</i> = 1.04 Pre–3m: 11.46** (6.66 to 16.26); <i>d</i> = 1.28 Post–3m: 1.57 (–0.94 to 4.09); <i>d</i> = –0.28
	G ₀	13.73 ± 8.85	5.82 ± 5.56	3.41 ± 4.75	Pre–post: 7.91* (2.75 to 13.06); <i>d</i> = 1.07 Pre–3m: 10.31** (5.1 to 15.53); <i>d</i> = 1.45 Post–3m: 2.41 (–0.32 to 5.15); <i>d</i> = –0.46
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	1.73 (–4.43 to 7.90); <i>d</i> = 0.16	–0.24 (–3.76 to 3.27); <i>d</i> = –0.04	0.59 (–2.10 to 3.28); <i>d</i> = –0.12	
TSK-11	G ₁	25.88 ± 5.97	17.73 ± 4.19	18.18 ± 4.79	Pre–post: 8.15** (5.94 to 10.36); <i>d</i> = 1.58 Pre–3m: 7.69** (5.35 to 10.02); <i>d</i> = 1.42 Post–3m: –0.46 (–2.44 to 1.52); <i>d</i> = –0.1
	G ₀	27.55 ± 6.57	18.91 ± 4.44	17.95 ± 5.63	Pre–post: 8.63** (6.23 to 11.03); <i>d</i> = 1.54 Pre–3m: 9.59** (7.05 to 12.12); <i>d</i> = 1.57 Post–3m: 0.95 (–1.2 to 3.11); <i>d</i> = 0.19
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	–1.66 (–5.30 to 1.98); <i>d</i> = –0.26	–1.17 (–3.69 to 6.48); <i>d</i> = –0.27	0.23 (–2.79 to 3.26); <i>d</i> = 0.04	
CPSS	G ₁	145.54 ± 29.95	164.04 ± 20.02	164.79 ± 24.36	Pre–post: 18.5** (–29.61 to –7.37); <i>d</i> = –0.72 Pre–3m: 19.25* (–31.10 to –7.39); <i>d</i> = –0.70 Post–3m: –0.75 (–6.79 to 5.29); <i>d</i> = –0.03
	G ₀	137.28 ± 35.35	162.04 ± 27.93	165.85 ± 32.76	Pre–post: –24.76** (–36.64 to –12.88); <i>d</i> = –0.77 Pre–3m: –28.57** (–41.24 to –15.89); <i>d</i> = –0.83 Post–3m: –3.81 (–10.26 to 2.64); <i>d</i> = –0.12
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	8.25 (–11.37 to 27.88); <i>d</i> = 0.25	1.99 (–12.48 to 16.47); <i>d</i> = 0.08	–1.06 (–18.29 to 16.15); <i>d</i> = –0.03	
RMDQ	G ₁	6.35 ± 4.75	1.77 ± 1.96	1.88 ± 3.12	Pre–post: 4.57** (2.91 to 6.24); <i>d</i> = 1.26 Pre–3m: 4.46** (2.85 to 6.07); <i>d</i> = 1.11 Post–3m: –0.11 (–0.90 to 0.66); <i>d</i> = –0.04
	G ₀	5.25 ± 3.12	1.46 ± 1.18	0.83 ± 1.66	Pre–post: 3.79** (2.06 to 5.52); <i>d</i> = 1.60 Pre–3m: 4.41** (2.74 to 6.09); <i>d</i> = 1.76 Post–3m: 0.62 (–0.19 to 1.44); <i>d</i> = 0.43
Mean difference (95% CI); effect size	G ₁ vs G ₀	1.09 (–1.21 to 3.40); <i>d</i> = 0.27	0.31 (–0.62 to 1.24); <i>d</i> = 0.19	1.05 (–0.39 to 2.49); <i>d</i> = 0.42	

3m = three months postintervention; CPSS = Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; G₀ = control group; G₁ = experimental group; PCS = Pain Catastrophizing Scale; Post = postintervention; Pre = pre-intervention; RMDQ = Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire; TSK-11 = Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia.

P* < 0.01; *P* < 0.001.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Study flow chart.

Figure 2. Changes in intake medication.

Figure 3. Changes in Pain Catastrophizing Scale. 3 month = 3-month post-treatment measure; Con = control group; Exp = experimental group; PCS-H = Pain Catastrophizing Scale–Helplessness subscale; PCS-M = Pain Catastrophizing Scale–Magnification subscale; PCS-R = Pain Catastrophizing Scale–Rumination subscale; Pre = pretreatment measure; Post = post-treatment measure.

Figure 4. Changes in Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia. 3 month = 3-month post-treatment measure; Con = control group; Exp = experimental group; Pre = pretreatment measure; Post = post-treatment measure; TSK-FA = Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia–Fear of Activity subscale; TSK-FH = Tampa Scale of Kinesiophobia–Fear of Harm subscale.

Figure 5. Changes in Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale. 3 month = 3-month post-treatment measure; Con = control group; Exp = experimental group; CPSS-CS = Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale-Coping with Symptoms subscale; CPSS-PF = Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale-Physical Functioning subscale; CPSS-PM = Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale-Pain Management subscale; Pre = pre-treatment measure; Post = post-treatment measure.

Figure 6. Global Rating of Change scale.

Annexed 1: TPE Protocol

SESSION 1	Neuromatrix of pain. Difference between acute pain and chronic pain. Pain and damage. Pain and Nociception. Importance of TPE.
SESSION 3	Pain and context. Influence of maladaptive beliefs and psychosocial factors.
SESSION 5	Pain and memory. Hypervigilance. Active Coping Strategies.
SESSION 7	Pain and age. Pain and culture. Pain and gender. Central and Peripheral sensitization. Neuroplasticity.
SESSION 8	Review of acquired concepts. Active Coping Strategies.

Annexed 2: Behavioral Training Protocol

	Experimental motor restructuring: Technique in which using a mirror, the patient was asked for a painful movement using a distraction strategy to cause a decrease in symptoms. It was used with the aim of desensitizing fear, promoting active coping and increasing self-efficacy.
SESSION 2	Sensory reinterpretation: Technique in which, through a numerical scale, the patient was asked to quantify his level of pain. Subsequently, a re-conceptualization of the same was carried out. The same process as the sensations that accompany the pain (tension, fatigue, discomfort and dysesthesia) was then carried out and a training of the coping skills was performed for each one.
SESSION 4	Jacobson Progressive Relaxation: Technique in which the therapist teaches the patient to contract and relax different muscle groups as a coping strategy in the face of stress and tension.
SESSION 6	Motor imagery and observation of actions: Technique in which a protocol of observation of actions in the movements of the lumbar spine was realized through a video, to later carry out a process of kinesthetic imagination.

Annexed 3: TE Protocol

Exercise 1:	Description:
Anteversion and retroversion pelvic with lumbar stabilization. Repetitions: 10-12. Series: 3-4 series.	In supine position, the patient makes an inspiration, later, he performs a pelvic retroversion by performing a lumbar stabilization to attach the lumbar spine to the mat in the expiratory phase.

Exercise 2:	Description:
Lumbar lift with feet supported ("The bridge"). Repetitions: 10-12. Series: 3-4 series. Rest: Active. A movement is made with the legs to one side and the opposite while the feet are supported on the ground (10 on each side).	In supine position, the patient makes an inspiration, later, he performs a pelvic retroversion, performing a lumbar stabilization to attach the lumbar spine to the mat. From this position, a lumbar elevation is performed during exhalation, until the weight is supported on the shoulders. The reverse position is reversed.

Exercise 3:	Description:
<p>Leg elevation 90°-90°: Repetitions: 10-12. Series: 3-4 series. Rest: Active. A stretching of the gluteus muscle (10sg per leg) and the pyramidal muscle (10sg per leg) is performed.</p>	<p>In a supine position, the patient performs an inspiration, later he performs a lumbar stabilization and while during exhaling, a hip flexion is performed until the leg is placed 90° hip flexion and 90° knee flexion. Both legs alternate with each repetition</p>

Exercise 4:	Description:
<p>Elevation of arm and leg in quadruped. Repetitions: 8-12. Series: 3-4 series. Rest: Active. A stretching of the paravertebral musculature is performed for 30sec.</p>	<p>In quadruped, the patient takes an inspiration, later elevating one arm and the opposite leg, performing a previous contraction of the lumbar stabilizing muscles and in the expiratory phase. Each arm and the opposite leg alternate in each repetition.</p>

Exercise 5:	Description:
<p>Step from sitting to standing. Repetitions: 8-12. Series: 3-4 series. Rest: Active. In quadruped, a movement of the rachis is made from flexion to extension (10 times).</p>	<p>Sitting on the edge of the chair. The patient is asked to look for a neutral position of the pelvis, keeping the feet resting on the floor with one of them advanced over the other. After the inspiration, a lumbar stabilization is performed and, advancing the body, is asked to be incorporated into a standing position. The return to sedestation is done in the same way, looking for the chair and the starting position.</p>

Annexed 4: MT Protocol

Technical	Description	Image
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**Postero-
anterior
mobilizations**

Passive mobilizations in the postero-anterior direction grade 1-2 at the vertebral level L4-L5 with a velocity of 2 Hz for 2 minutes, 3 sets. (68)

**Bilateral
lumbo-pelvic
traction**

Bilateral lumbo-pelvic traction oscillatory with cinch for 2 minutes at a rate of 2 Hz in cranial-caudal direction looking for a decompression effect of both the lumbar region and the coxo-femoral joint during 3 sets. (69,70)

**Mobilization
of the neural
tube**

Sliding of the neural tube alternating near-distal tensions at speed of between 0.5 Hz and 1 Hz performing 3 sets of 10 repetitions. When the physiotherapist prints a craniocervical flexion with an anteroposterior mobilization in the thoracic region, the patient

maintains knee flexion. In contrast, when the physiotherapist brings the craniocervical and thoracic region to the initial position, the patient extends the leg over the opposite side. (71)

Coxo-femoral traction with movement

Distraction technique of the lateral coxo-femoral joint maintained by a cinch, in turn the physiotherapist performs a passive mobilization in internal rotation of the same. The volume and frequency is: 3 sets of 12 repetitions.

